

MIXING LIVESTOCK IN A FOREST/SILVOPASTORALISM

1. Mixed herd of cattle and goats in Valaora (Regional unit of Evrytania), Photo G. Bakogiorgos 2. Sheep and goats coexist in Greece, Photo Anastasia Pantera 3. Mixed grazing of sheep and goats in mount Timfristos (Regional unit of Evrytania). Photo V. Lappa 4. Mixed livestock farming is popular in the Mediterranean basin. Picture from Lebanon. Photo A. Pantera

WHAT AND WHY

Mixed grazing refers to the practice of grazing two or more species of animals—such as cows, goats, and sheep—together at the same time. In Greece, the establishment of mixed flocks of sheep and goats has been a common tradition for thousands of years, primarily to improve pasture use and promote sustainable management. This practice takes advantage of the different dietary preferences of sheep and goats. Although their diets overlap considerably, they are not identical: sheep prefer grasses, while goats tend to browse on woody vegetation that sheep avoid. This complementary grazing helps maintain the balance of the pasture, preventing the dominance of invasive plant species. Mixed herds, especially within agroforestry systems, also contribute to the natural reduction of dry biomass in the understory and help control shrubby vegetation. This reduces the risk of wildfires and clears space for cultivating cereals or vegetables.

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

The establishment of mixed flocks of goats and sheep is generally easy, as these two species coexist well. However, combining small ruminants with cattle—forming what is called a “flerd” (flock + herd)—is more challenging. Small ruminants often avoid cattle, especially near water sources. This challenge can be addressed in two ways: either through forced cohabitation in confined spaces, as seen in the village of Stenoma in Evrytania, or by using special techniques to create a “bond” between the sheep or goats and the cattle. Developing such a bond involves allowing young goats or sheep to live with cattle inside a stable, with an “emergency exit” available at all times. When successfully established, this bond is strong enough that a flock of sheep will follow any herd of cattle, rather than specific individual animals.

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ADVANTAGES

Mixed grazing provides several advantages, including more efficient pasture use, as different animal species feed on different plants or different parts of the same plants. In agroforestry systems, reducing understory biomass lowers the risk of fire and frees up land for crop cultivation. Adding a second species to a pasture can improve the overall utilization of available forage. For example, studies show that a flock of 200–300 sheep can graze alongside a herd of 200 cattle without reducing the cattle's productivity, while enhancing the farm's economic performance.

Mixed grazing offers several additional benefits. It supports effective weed control and improves soil fertility and health. Studies also suggest that mixed grazing increases biodiversity and helps reduce methane emissions, a major greenhouse gas. In the USA, "flerds" (mixed herds of cattle and small ruminants) are promoted to enhance protection against large predators, with cattle acting as a natural "barrier."

Another important advantage is the reduced risk from toxic plants—since one species may consume plants that are harmful to the other, they help protect each other. Various combinations of animals bring further benefits. For instance, chickens grazing among cattle consume fly larvae found in manure while producing eggs and meat. Similarly, herds of black pigs adapt well to oak agroforestry systems.

Mixed herds also increase the resilience of the farming operation. The outbreak of a disease affecting one species is less likely to wipe out the entire herd, thereby reducing business risk. Overall, mixed grazing of cattle and small ruminants is an effective strategy for managing limited space—especially in mountainous regions where land competition and conflicts among livestock farmers are common.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Beyond traditional sheep and goat flocks, mixed herds—or "flerds"—and other species combinations can be established to work synergistically within agroforestry systems.**
- **Enhanced pasture utilization leads to improved farm productivity and reduces business risk through diversification.**
- **Mixed grazing provides better natural defense against predators, parasites, and toxic plants.**

. Mixed livestock farming in public forest area near Lake Kremaston.
Photo G. Bakogiorgos

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